

A Funeral Ceremony as Part of the Life Cycle Ritual among the Cham Islam Community in Tan Chau, An Giang Province, Vietnam

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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ABSTRACT

Different cultures may exist among different groups. Culture is a term that refers to a group of people's way of life, or the way they do things. Learning passes on a culture to the next generation, whereas heredity passes on genetics. A person's life cycle ritual includes a funeral, which is both significant and culturally significant. Funeral traditions are a set of beliefs and practices that a community uses to commemorate and honor the dead, ranging from intercessions to memorials, prayers, and rituals. This research adopted a sequential explanatory approach that combines qualitative and quantitative approaches. The first is a quantitative method for determining the number of households participating in the ceremony. The data is gathered by a household survey, which involves employing a questionnaire to collect information from a sample of households in the population.

Keywords: FUNERAL CEREMONY, MOSQUE, CLOAKING CORPSES, PRAYER

Introduction

The Cham people are one of the ethnic groups in Vietnam that have significantly contributed to the cultural diversity of the country. Although their culture has changed in various aspects today, the Cham culture attract many scholars (1). As now, they live in the provinces and cities of Ninh Thuan, Binh Thuan, Ho Chi Minh, Tay Ninh, An Giang, where An Giang is considered the place with the largest number of Cham people in the West, the southern region with a Muslim majority (2). Different groups may have different cultures. Culture is a word for the way of life of groups of people, meaning the way they do things. A culture is passed on to the next generation by learning, whereas genetics are passed on by heredity. Culture is seen in people's writing, religion, music, clothes, cooking, and what they do (3). In an ethnic group, the customs, practices or religious rituals are also one of the cultural characteristics of

that community. The life cycle ritual is one of the rituals that we can clearly perceive in their daily lives. Those are the rituals that are always associated with the life cycle of each person, the rituals that mark each stage of development of each individual in the community. People have established a belief system and a ritual system in response to the requirements of the spiritual life, in response to both dread and longing for the gods' grace. A funeral is a significant and culturally significant aspect of a person's life cycle ritual. Funeral traditions are a collection of beliefs and activities used by a community to remember and honour the dead, ranging from intercessions to memorials, prayers, and rituals performed in their honor. Cultures and religious groups have different customs. Funerals are held to honor the deceased, celebrate their lives, and offer support and condolences to those who have lost loved ones.

The research is a scientific study of the life cycle rituals of the Cham Islam community and will contribute significantly to the knowledge of the practice of rituals. The research paper will provide specific information on the life cycle rituals of the Cham people in general and the Cham Islam in An Giang in particular. At the same time, it also contributes to providing material in the future study of Cham culture.

Materials and methods

Ritual is a way, a method of performing a custom based on divine and spiritual factors. Rituals also create and nurture beliefs, social customs, and religions, because the ritual is a cultural or religious activity. Rituals can be private or performed in groups, performances attendees, and attendees and appropriate rituals will match their customs and culture. As content, rituals are all that are associated with religious ceremonies, such as births, deaths, weddings, and daily rituals to embody the sacredness of treatment itself special is required (4). Different forms of rituals have been classified by culturalists: The agricultural ritual system prays for favorable weather and good crops. Ritual system in fishery beliefs; ritual system according to ancestral beliefs, ancestor worship ritual, religious community ritual and life cycle ritual system. Almost every human being living in any society has to go through many different stages according to his biological cycle, such as: birth, growing up, getting married, giving birth, growing old and dying. The transition between stages is usually accomplished by a certain type of ritual, called a life-cycle ritual (5).

Funerals are a common form among most people, and rituals and beliefs about the dead play an important role in all religions, from primitive forms to ancient ones and the most complex religions. Funerals in most cultures are not only family members, but also people in the community, even new acquaintances, weep, mourn, etc. These are official acts, due to customs. The custom requires all members of the community, especially relatives and families. Because when someone dies, not only the family is weakened, but the entire community loses a member, that is, a part of its strength. At that time, the community needed to worship (funeral rites) to regroup, to revive, and to assert itself (6).

This research uses sequential explanatory by mixing qualitative and quantitative methods. First, the quantitative method to find out the number of household performing the ritual. The data collection is conducted through household survey, which is collecting data from household samples in the population by using a questionnaire.

The questioner record occupation, income, composition members, and health status of the household. The number of samples is determined by using random sampling.

Conclusion

1: History of Cham Islam community in An Giang

1.1: History of the Cham people in Vietnam

The Cham people have lived in the central region of Vietnam since medieval times, and they once built a powerful country - the Kingdom of Champa (Chiem Thanh) - which is still remembered books to this day. The Champa Kingdom, also known as the Lam Ap in ancient Chinese history, was founded in AD 192. Champa's territory narrowed and retreated southward from the tenth century onwards as a result of conflicts and skirmishes with countries in the region at the time, particularly the exchanges contested with Dai Viet.

Before the seventh century, a kingdom known as Lam Ap of the Cham people flourished from the third year of the Han Dynasty (192) to the first year of the Sui Dynasty (191). After 605, Lam Ap experienced many changes, particularly the continuous construction of the pagoda and the construction of Sanskrit stele, and history began to become clear. The history of the Champa kingdom included conflicts with China, Dai Viet, Khmer and Mongolia, as well as internal conflicts. It was due to these conflicts that Champa gradually lost territory to Dai Viet, a country with a better government and military organization. The Champa are good warriors who have used the mountainous terrain to dominate. In the second year of Hong Duc (1471), the emirate of Vijaya suffered heavy losses in the war with Dai Viet under the reign of King Le Thanh Tong (7). In the years 1854-1858, Cambodians were forced to relocate more and more to Chau Doc (An Giang) as a result of ongoing rebellions. When the Cham people and the Melayu in Cambodia travelled to Vietnam to be taken home and executed by King Chan Lap at the request of the Nguyen Dynasty, Tuon Seth Asmit led the Cham people and the Melayu in Cambodia against the Nguyen Dynasty. Tuon Seth Little rebelled because he was dissatisfied with the king's treatment of his father. Tuon Set Less and their companions and families (both Cham and Do Ba) retreated to Chau Doc after the uprising failed. The Cham people were distributed to seven villages by the Nguyen Dynasty: Chau Giang, Katambong, Phum Xoai, La Ma, Kacoi, Ka Coki (7).

1.2 The process of forming a Cham Muslim community in An Giang

An Giang is a province located at the headwaters of the Mekong River basin with the characteristics of being an agricultural province, with both plains and hills, and a border with Cambodia nearly 100km long. An Giang has the largest population in the Southwest region, ranking 6th in Vietnam. An Giang is also the province with the largest number of Cham Muslims living in the South. According to statistics on religious work in An Giang, the province currently has 15,327 Cham followers of Islam (the Steering Committee of the Congress of Ethnic Minority Deputies of An Giang Province, 2019).

How the Cham people of An Giang were formed until now still has many different opinions, but based on some ethnographic documents and preserved artifacts, especially the decision to verify the ethnic community of the General Statistics Office of Vietnam dated 2/3/1979, we can say that the Cham people in An Giang and the

Cham people in the South Central region (Ninh Thuan, Binh Thuan), share a long historical origin (8). The Cham people, according to archaeologists, were originally from the Malay-Da Dao lineage, an island civilization that received the influence of the Indo-Islamic culture, which is still matriarchal today. They migrated to South Central and South Vietnam centuries BC, bringing and preserving all their customs and matriarchal family systems.

Based on a number of ancient bibliographies, ethnographic materials, some Cham folk songs remembered by the ethnic group, some preserved artifacts and ancient texts, comparison of ethnology and the history of migration, especially the decision to verify the ethnic community of the General Statistics Office of Vietnam dated 2-3-1979, allows the conclusion: Cham people in An Giang and Cham people in the South Central region have the same calendar origin, from a long time ago, including the Cham people of Ho Chi Minh City, Tay Ninh and Cambodia. The Cham community in An Giang follows Islam, strictly adheres to the canon law of orthodox Islam, and has faith in Allah, the Prophet Muhammad and the Quran. Currently, in An Giang, there are 12 mosques, 1 vihara (new religion), 13 minor churches, 11 teachers, 22 assistant professors, 13 Ahly and 116 positions.

Chau Phong commune belongs to Tan Chau town, consisting of eight hamlets and 24,234 people, of which three hamlets live among Cham people, including Chau Giang hamlet, Phom Soai hamlet, and Hoa Long hamlet, with a Cham population of 4,615 people, accounting for 19% of the population of the whole Chau Phong commune, accounting for 32.5% of the population of the Cham people in An Giang province. Prior to 2010, Chau Giang Hamlet was part of Phu Hiep commune in Chau Phu district, but it was moved to Chau Phong commune for easier management. Hoa Long hamlet (Hoa Long residential area) now includes about 40 households of Cham people (9).

2 Funeral ceremonial in the life of Cham Muslims in Tan Chau, An Giang

2.1: The Cham people's notion of death

Each ethnic group has a series of conversion rituals with different content and forms of expression depending on the social class, gender, occupation, age, of the individuals who are performing that ritual. The transformation of the ceremony is divided into three stages: isolation (before the threshold), transition (beyond the threshold), and integration (threshold).

The Cham people, unlike some other ethnic groups in Vietnam, do not celebrate longevity or old age since, as previously stated, life is merely a fleeting realm with nothing worthy of attachment and devotion. They are also unconcerned or unprepared for their demise. When a family member is dying or near death, the family will place them in the west, facing the great holy Mecca, to pray to Allah for forgiveness of their sins. "According to the Islamic belief, when a person dies, their soul will be probed by two gods, Monkar and Nakir, so the dead person must be washed clean to preparation for this sacred interrogation," said Shahot Hamid, deputy deacon of the Nia'mah mosque.

.2.2 The procedure of completing a Cham Islam funeral ceremony in Tan Chau, An Giang.

If a relative dies in the morning, Muslims usually bury them in the afternoon, or pick the next morning if they died the previous day. The body will be transported to the cemetery on a plank used to bathe the corpse, rather than in a discrete casket, by four persons. The funeral would be led by knowledgeable, reputable members of the devout, who would hum brief lyrics with a religious rhythm (10).

Normally, men will bathe men, women will bathe women, and proceed to bathe three times, the last time with apple leaf water. After bathing, proceed to the water to prostrate to help the dead prepare for the next step in the afterlife. The following are records of actual observations and the account of Uncle Goxali of the rituals at the funeral of a Cham Muslim.

***Preparing for the corpse**

Funeral rites of the Cham people are conducted within 24 hours after the person dies. When a person dies, people will rub their face and use water to wipe their face (pagalau). Then recite an Arabic prayer with the meaning: "You have come back to God!"

The cloth will then secure the deceased's chin to prevent it from falling. They also adjust the legs, hands, knees, and ankles, as well as two hands, to match the style of the event. The person in charge will next place a heavy object on the dead person's stomach, such as a blue stone (4x6) or an iron scissor, to prevent wind from making the stomach inflate. Then cover it with a blanket, place a mosquito net over it, and point the dead person's feet toward Mecca. After that, the family will inform relatives and neighbors that the person has died. A Quran or two is always placed next to the corpse. The goal is to offer people one last chance to observe the body before it is buried with Quranic inscriptions. According to the Goxali mantra, it is best to read a whole scripture. Each person only reads a paragraph and then marks it for the next person to continue reading until they have finished reading one sutra.

*** Bathing the corpse**

Before bathing the corpse, prepare the following items: unscented soap, 3 white cloths, cotton wool, mothballs and camphor mixed with shaved cypress bark. Spread two white cloths stacked on top of each other, followed by a layer of cotton wool, then spread a layer of mothballs mixed with cypress bark, making a pillow for the dead.

***Regulations for bathing dead people**

Cham Islam people do not bathe the corpse with scented soap and, at the same time, do not flush the water backwards, from top to bottom. The shroud will flex the corpse's body when the initial water bath is over, pushing the dirt out. The dead individual will be washed with soap and then showered with apple leaf water after the dirt has been removed. Finally, bow to the corpse with water. This indicates that the living assist the deceased in preparing for the sholat rite to be performed in the afterlife.

*** Cloaking corpses**

For men, they are covered in three layers of fabric, and their pilgrim clothing are buried with them if they are pilgrims. There are five layers of shrouds for women, including three layers of white cloth and a set of offerings that includes a headscarf. The deceased's face will be left open before burial so that relatives can see him or her

one more time, and the family can kiss the deceased's forehead as a final goodbye.

The body will next be wrapped and packed into five joints: two heads, hands, hips, and knees. Because the Prophet Muhammad enjoyed odd numbers, the usage of odd numbers in burial customs such as 3 shrouds, linking the dead to 5, is explained.

Picture 1: The process of preparing the shroud to wrap the corpse

***Ceremony at the mosque**

A prayer service is held at the mosque for the deceased. The Hakim, neighbors, and other believers of the dead attend this ritual. The number of attendees is determined by the deceased's relatives. Typically, the village's headteacher will preside over the ritual and read the Qur'an in order to pray for and send the deceased to the afterlife. The individual performing the ceremony stands rather than kneels in this prayer, which is different from the everyday ceremony. Following that, someone will arrive with buckets of earth and small round balls to distribute to everyone attending the burial. As a farewell and companionship, attendees will blow onto lumps of earth and recite a prayer from the Qur'an.. Attendees will blow into lumps of earth and recite a prayer from the Qur'an as a farewell and companionship to the dead, which will then be buried with them.

Picture 2: Ritual of praying for the dead in the mosque

When a Muslim dies, he will be buried in a cemetery near the mosque according to the provisions of Islamic law in the Qur'an. The dead person's grave will be dug about 1m8 or more above the head in the north-south direction, with the dead person's head facing north and the dead person's feet facing south. The dead person will then be placed in this hole in the posture of lying on their side, left side below, right upper body facing west, towards Mecca.

Then the five knots will be untied, the cloth will be removed from the face and a lump of earth will be made to press against the cheek of the dead person. On the foot side, the toes will be opened and a lump of earth will be pressed to touch the toes. These earthen lumps are the round lumps of earth of people who attended the funeral after reciting prayers and were buried with the deceased. Letting the cheeks and toes touch the ground means: "Man is born from the earth, and will eventually return to the earth". After that, people will use a board to cover the mouth of the hole to cover the corpse's body and fill it with soil. The graves of the dead will be placed on two terraces, on both sides of the head and feet.

***A type of remembrance for the deceased**

According to Mr. Sukari, who works for the Ethnic Minority Committee of An Giang province, following the burial, people can perform a three-night ceremony at the temple to pray for the dead, depending on family circumstances. There is no established date for remembering the dead, according to Islamic traditions.. Because Sholat is considered a day of prayer for all souls every Friday, each family can create a memorial day for the departed on any day, based on their wishes and circumstances. It is less complicated than having family or friends visit the deceased's tomb and read the Qur'an. Uncle Mukhtar, an assistant professor at the Azhar mosque, explains that this is because the dead are unable to read the Qur'an. As a result, the living will read on behalf of the deceased, hoping that Allah will witness and consider the prayers recited by the dead; this act is a way for the living to express their hearts and affection for the dead.

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